

RESISTANCE AND STRAIN RESISTANCE PROPERTIES OF SOLID SOLUTIONS $TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe_2$ ($0 \leq x \leq 0.5$)

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Abstract: The paper presents the results of a study of the effect of the ratio of cobalt components on the electro-physical and strain-resistive characteristics of $TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe_2$ alloys in the concentration range of cobalt $x = 0 - 0.5$. It is established that in the range of $x = 0 - 0.02$ these properties have linear concentration dependencies, which undergo sharp changes in the range of $0.02 - 0.5$.

It was found that with an increase in temperature in the region of $300 \leq T \leq 410$ K, the sensitivity to deformation in all investigated compositions of the solid solution $TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe_2$ significantly increases.

Keywords: ratios of cobalt components, electro-physical, strain-resistive characteristics, concentration range.

Introduction: In the study of various properties of solid materials, an important place is occupied by the study of their tensometric properties. Investigation of the tensor resistive properties of semiconductors and dielectric compounds allows obtaining information about their band structure, local centers of color, capture, recombination, etc. According to the study of the tensometric properties of complex semiconductor materials, including $A^{III}B^{III}C_2^{VI}$ and solid solutions based on them, $TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe_2$ makes it possible to create highly sensitive miniature strain gauges.

The use of strain gauges in various fields of science and technology brings

significant benefits to the national economy. With the help of a flexible measuring instrument, characterized by simplicity, reliability, speed, stability, efficiency, small overall dimensions and weight, low cost, various tasks are successfully solved, such as studies of constant and variable elastic and plastic deformations, measuring mechanical stresses in various crystallographic axes, forces, pressures, moments and other physical parameters. Currently, more than 80% of transducers of mechanical quantities use strain gages.

The successes of modern electronics, in particular, integrated microelectronics, which provide the possibility of creating inexpensive compact and highly sensitive reliable amplifiers and converters for matching the low-power output of strain gauges with the actuators of electronic automation devices, have contributed to the increasing use of strain gauge devices and systems for automatic control, signaling and regulation of various technological and testing processes, diagnostics of equipment, including human organs.

However, the existing information in the literature on strain gauge does not sufficiently reflect the questions of the practical application of strain gages in specific systems of industrial automation, astronautics, modern medicine, etc., cannot answer with the necessary completeness the questions that arise when designing the use of strain gages devices.

There is almost no systematic information in the literature. Therefore, the growing needs of modern micro- and optoelectronics stimulate the development of scientific research in the direction of searching for new semiconductor materials, which have, in particular, the specific structure of the crystal lattice. These materials include low-dimensional chalcogenides with layered and chain structures. Recently, many interesting features of their electrical, photoelectric, optical, and tensoresistive properties have been revealed, as well as the prospects for their practical use. However, to date, their potential is far from being fully disclosed.

In this regard, the purpose of this work is to determine the resistivity and tensorial properties of solid solutions $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ on the concentration of cobalt is important.

Samples for research and experimental: Large homogeneous pure and doped TlInSe_2 single crystals and solid solutions based on them $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ ($0 \leq x \leq 0.5$), required for physical studies, were grown by Dr. Sci. Umarov S. Kh. at the Institute of Physics of the National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan using the improved Bridgman - Stockbarger method [1 - 3].

The initial materials for the synthesis were elements of special purity: thallium (Tl - 000); cobalt (Co - 000), indium (In - 000), selenium (OSCh - 17 - 4). Crystals grew in evacuated (up to 10^{-4} mm. rt. st.) and sealed quartz ampoules. Melting zone temperature when growing single crystals was $T_1 = 1060$ K, the annealing temperature was $T_2 = 960$ K, a temperature gradient of 25 deg / cm was created in the crystallization zone.

The authors of [2] managed to grow single crystals with the desired geometric configurations of various sizes, and perfect thin plates of the grown single crystals turned out to be flexible enough and withstand bending with a radius of curvature of about 3 mm. Table 1 shows the growth modes and some characteristics of the obtained TlInSe_2 and $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ single crystals ($0 \leq x \leq 0.5$). The crystals obtained in this way were easily cleaved along the basal plane and had a mirror-smooth surface.

Table 1. Growing mode and some characteristics single crystals of solid solutions $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$

Co conce ntrati on, x	Temperature zone, T, K		Speed crystalliz ation, mm / hour	Single crystal sizes, mm ³	Conduct ivity type	ρ , at 300K, Om·cm	ρ , at 77K, Om·s m
	I zone	II zone					

0	1110-	1015-	0,9-1,0	60x15x8	p	$6,4 \cdot 10^6$	$1,9 \cdot 1$
0,1	1020	910	- " - " -	60x15x8	p	$4,0 \cdot 10^6$	0^9
0,2	1090-	1010-	- " - " -	60x15x6	p	$2,5 \cdot 10^4$	$2,0 \cdot 1$
0,3	1020	890	- " - " -	60x12x8	p	$4,4 \cdot 10^4$	0^9
0,4	1070-	1000-	- " - " -	60x15x6	p	$2,3 \cdot 10^4$	$3,3 \cdot 1$
0,5	1015	850	- " - " -	60x12x8	p	$2,8 \cdot 10^3$	0^6
	1070-	990-					$3,5 \cdot 1$
	1010	860					0^7
	1060-	980-					$3,6 \cdot 1$
	1010	860					0^6
	1050-	970-					$3,1 \cdot 1$
	1010	850					0^5

Manufacturing technology of semiconductor strain gauges is very complex, time consuming and requires high costs. Difficulties are mainly caused by the cutting and processing of the necessary whiskers, which are inevitably accompanied by such time-consuming operations as mechanical cutting of materials, grinding of workpieces, special chemical treatment (to remove a mechanically damaged surface layer after grinding, chemical-dynamic etching is usually used) and, finally, finishing of workpieces for strain gages. The specificity of the crystal structural features of the TlInSe_2 layered crystals and solid solutions based on them, i.e. folded semiconductors, systems makes it possible to manufacture strain gauges using a very simple technology that does not require the laborious operations listed above.

The task is simplified by the use of "fresh" chips, split without much difficulty from a massive ingot of standard thin strain-sensitive plates with opposite vertical mirror edges of natural cleavage (section $0.01 - 0.2 \text{ mm}^2$, length $1 - 40 \text{ mm}$).

The identical crystals necessary for the study were obtained by us by the simplest

indentation of a sharp knife with a blade thickness of ≤ 0.01 mm onto the loose end of a thin but wide and long single crystal plate at an angle of 45° .

After setting the selected step, which determines the width of the blanks along the hair lines, the semiconductor plate, together with the micromanipulator stage, moves under the microscope across the cleavage line. The "needle" crystals obtained by this method are obtained with mirror faces without any additional processing and are ready for welding the leads and planting them on the base of the substrate.

When soldering "antennae", i.e. when creating mechanically reliable ohmic contacts on the above blanks, two methods were used:

1) direct spot welding of the corresponding wires with a capacitor discharge to the ends of the workpiece heated in a flow of inert gas;

2) fusion of indium onto the workpiece in an inert gas flow, followed by brazing of nickel or copper wires with a diameter of $\varnothing = 0.01$ mm.

The first method turned out to be more reliable and efficient (especially for moderate temperatures).

Steel plates 45, 20 mm to 80 mm long and 0.5 to 1 mm thick, were used as calibration beams for gluing the sensors. According to the processing class, the surface of the substrate corresponded to class 7. Medium - carbon steel of grade 45 contains 0.45% carbon, and the remaining impurities are extremely insignificant, and therefore steel of this grade has increased strength and belongs to structurally high-quality materials.

Research results and discussion: We have studied the effect of the Co impurity concentration on some electro-physical and tensoresistive characteristics of crystals of the $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ system at the concentration values $x = 0 - 0.5$ [4 - 6].

Table 2 shows the results of measurements of the electro-physical properties of alloys of the $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ system in the range of cobalt concentration $x = 0 -$

0.5. The data obtained show that the resistivity ρ of the concentration x of cobalt in the intervals $x = 0 - 0.02$ and $0.02 - 0.5$ decreases linearly, forming a characteristic break at the concentration $x = 0.02$ (see Fig. 1).

Table 2. Electro-physical parameters of $TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe_2$ crystals

Load cell crystal compositions	$TlInSe_2$	$TlIn_{0,99}Co_{0,01}Se_2$	$TlIn_{0,98}Co_{0,02}Se_2$	$TlIn_{0,97}Co_{0,03}Se_2$	$TlIn_{0,95}Co_{0,05}Se_2$	$TlIn_{0,9}Co_{0,1}Se_2$	$TlIn_{0,7}Co_{0,3}Se_2$	$TlIn_{0,5}Co_{0,5}Se_2$
Specific resistance, $\Omega \cdot cm$	$6400 \cdot 10^4$	$3300 \cdot 10^4$	$510 \cdot 10^4$	$480 \cdot 10^4$	$460 \cdot 10^4$	$400 \cdot 10^4$	$194 \cdot 10^4$	$0,28 \cdot 10^4$
Sample sizes, mm^3	60x15x8	60x15x8	60x15x6	60x12x8	60x15x6	60x15x8	60x15x6	60x12x8

Fig.1. Dependence of the resistivity ρ of the $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ alloys on the concentration of Co

In the concentration dependences of the strain-gage coefficient K_ε , a break also occurs precisely at the cobalt concentration $x = 0.02$ (see Table 3 and Fig. 2).

In the study of the nominal resistivity, resistivity and tensosensitivity coefficients of the $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ alloys in the concentration range $x = 0 - 0.5$, it was found that these properties undergo sharp changes at the cobalt concentration $x = 0.02$. On the one hand, TlInSe_2 compounds crystallize according to the tetragonal system with the lattice parameters $a = 8.075 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.847 \text{ \AA}$ [7], and the TlCoSe_2

Table 3. Tensosensitivity coefficients K_ε of solid solutions $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ ($0 \leq x \leq 0.5$) in comparison with TlInSe_2 crystals along the [001] axis

№	Load Cell Crystal Composition	K_ε , in compression	K_ε , under tension	Note
1.	TlInSe_2	577	406	With relative deformation $\varepsilon = 0,57 \cdot 10^{-3}$ T = 300K
2.	$\text{TlIn}_{0,99}\text{Co}_{0,01}\text{Se}_2$	1741	4041	
3.	$\text{TlIn}_{0,98}\text{Co}_{0,02}\text{Se}_2$	2730	6800	
4.	$\text{TlIn}_{0,97}\text{Co}_{0,03}\text{Se}_2$	2760	6830	
5.	$\text{TlIn}_{0,95}\text{Co}_{0,05}\text{Se}_2$	2800	6849	
6.	$\text{TlIn}_{0,9}\text{Co}_{0,1}\text{Se}_2$	2839	6881	
7.	$\text{TlIn}_{0,7}\text{Co}_{0,3}\text{Se}_2$	2903	6993	
8.	$\text{TlIn}_{0,5}\text{Co}_{0,5}\text{Se}_2$	2951	7143	

Fig. 2. Dependences of the tensosensitivity coefficient of the $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ alloys along the [001] axis on the Co concentration

compounds - according to the hexagonal system with the parameters $a = 3.747 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 22.772 \text{ \AA}$ [8], on the other hand, due to the large difference in the sizes of the covalent ionic radii of indium (1.497 \AA) and cobalt (1.09 \AA); these two compounds cannot form an unrestricted solid solution, but can form only a limited solid solution in a narrow concentration range. Therefore, it is assumed that, by analogy with the $\text{Tl}_{1-x}\text{Cu}_x\text{InSe}_2$ system, in the $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ system at a concentration range of $x = 0 - 0.02$, limited solid solutions are formed, and in the range $x = 0.02 - 0.5$ alloys are multiphase. Therefore, when this boundary is crossed, a sharp change in the physical properties of the alloys occurs, which is reflected in the form of a break in the figures, and which indicates a sharp difference in the mechanisms of the above phenomena, the establishment of which requires special research.

As can be seen from Table 3, in all studied samples at room temperature, a

strong tensoresistive effect is manifested both during compression and when crystals are stretched in the [001] direction. The tensosensitivity coefficient at both positive and negative deformations increases with an increase in the concentration of Co in solid solutions $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$.

The temperature dependence of the resistance of the samples and the change in the coefficient of tensosensitivity on temperature are some of the important indicators of semiconductor strain gauge materials [9]. Therefore, the influence of the temperature of solid solutions on the coefficient of tensosensitivity was investigated in the temperature range $300\text{K} \leq T \leq 410\text{K}$. Experiments show that with an increase in the temperature of the samples, their sensitivity to deformation significantly increases in all the compositions of $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ solid solutions studied by us (see Table 4).

The temperature coefficients of the tensosensitivity per unit degree G_T in percent are given in table 5. The G_T of the studied crystals varied markedly from sample to sample, depending on the concentration of Co in the compounds.

Table 4. Tensosensitivity coefficients for compression of crystals $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ depending on the composition and temperature [5]

Nº	T, K	TlInSe_2	$\text{TlIn}_{0,99}\text{Co}_{0,01}\text{Se}_2$	$\text{TlIn}_{0,9}\text{Co}_{0,1}\text{Se}_2$	$\text{TlIn}_{0,5}\text{Co}_{0,5}\text{Se}_2$	Note
1	300	577	1741	2839	2951	With relative deformation $\varepsilon = 0,57 \cdot 10^{-3}$
2	320	586	2442	2930	3715	
3	350	592	3170	4691	5011	
4	375	610	3930	5184	5928	
5	410	655	4242	6088	7466	

Table 5. Temperature coefficient of tensosensitivity (G_T) of $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ crystals depending on composition

№	T _{cp} , K	TlInSe 2	TlIn _{0,99} Co _{0,01} S e ₂	TlIn _{0,9} Co _{0,1} S e ₂	TlIn _{0,5} Co _{0,5} Se ₂	Note
1.	310	0,078	2,01	1,43	0,86	$G_T = \frac{\Delta K / K_0}{\Delta T} \cdot 100\% ,$ $T_{cp} = 300 + \frac{1}{2} \Delta T$
2.	325	0,052	1,64	1,41	1,39	
3.	337,5	0,034	1,67	1,10	1,34	
4.	355	0,052	1,31	1,04	1,39	

The value of the temperature coefficient of the tensosensitivity substantially depends on the considered regions of the temperature interval. These results show that, in contrast to most semiconductor strain-gauge materials, in crystals of TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe₂ solid solutions, the sensitivity of the strain gauges can be increased with increasing temperature. Thus, strain gauges based on TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe₂ provide high registration accuracy under thermo stated operating conditions.

As already noted, the temperature dependence of the resistance and the change in the coefficient of strain gauge sensitivity with temperature are the most important indicators of semiconductor strain gauge materials. In the case of application of semiconductor strain gauges to parts with variable temperature, it becomes necessary to take into account and change the resistance and thermal change in the strain gauge coefficient of the sensors. Changes in the resistance of the sensor with temperature are taken into account by applying the appropriate compensation methods, and changes in the strain gauge sensitivity - by introducing a correction.

Studies have shown that the crystals of solid solutions of the TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe₂ system due to their relatively high tensosensitivity, significant flexibility, and the ability to chip into desired filamentous plates with mirror faces in the direction of the maximum tensoresistive effect [001], as well as due to the linear temperature dependence of the tensosensitivity in the range $300 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 410 \text{ K}$ are effective

materials for semiconductor strain gauge.

The above experimental results show that, in the single-phase region of the studied solid solutions, an increase in the concentration of copper or cobalt leads to a significant linear change in the resistivity, the coefficient of light resistance, and the coefficient of tensosensitivity of strain gauges made on the basis of TlInSe_2 crystals. Upon transition to the two-phase region, the properties of solid solutions change abruptly, which indicates a sharp difference in the mechanisms of the above phenomena in different concentration ranges of substitutional atoms.

Conclusion:

When studying the effect of the ratio of the components on the electro-physical and tensoresistive characteristics of $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ alloys in the concentration range of cobalt $x = 0 - 0.5$, it was found that in the range of $x = 0 - 0.02$ these properties have linear concentration dependences, which undergo sharp changes in the range $0.02 - 0.5$.

It is assumed that in the $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ system at the concentration range $x = 0 - 0.02$, limited solid solutions are formed, and in the range $x = 0.02 - 0.5$ alloys are multiphase. At room temperature, the tensosensitivity coefficient at both positive and negative strains along the $[001]$ direction increases with an increase in the Co concentration in $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ solid solutions.

It was found that with an increase in temperature in the region of $300 \leq T \leq 410$ K, the sensitivity to deformation in all investigated compositions of the solid solution $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ significantly increases.

Studies of the tensoresistive properties of crystals of solid solutions $\text{TlIn}_{1-x}\text{Co}_x\text{Se}_2$ in the range of cobalt concentration $0 \leq x \leq 0.5$, as well as the temperature dependence of the tensosensitivity of these crystals in the range $300 \leq T \leq 410$ K have shown their promise as effective materials for electronic engineering.

REFERENCES

1. Bekir Gürbulak, Cevdet Coşkun, Seydi Doğan, Aytunç Ateş, Yahya Kemal Yoğurtçu. The Growth of p-Type $A^{III} B^{III} C_2^{VI}$ Single Crystals // *Turkish Journal of Physics*. – Ankara, 2000. – No.24. –P.29-38.

2. Umarov S. X. Sintez i virashivanie monokristallov tverdix rastvorov $TlInS_{2x}Se_{2(1-x)}$ ($0 \leq x \leq 1$). //Preprint № 657 IYaF AN RUz.– Tashkent, 2003. – S.9.

3. Godjaev E. M., Djafarova S. R., Gyulmamedov K. D., Mamedov E. M., Osmanova S. S. Sintez i virahivanie monokristallov $TlInSe_2$ i $TlGaSe_2$. // *Izvestiya RAN, Neorganicheskie materialy*. – Moskva, 2009. – .45, № 7,– S.790 - 792.

4. Umarov S. X., Nuritdinov I., Ashurov J. D. Tenzorezistivnie svoystva tvyordix rastvorov $TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe_2$.// *Perspektivnie materialo`*. – Moskva, 2007. – №3. – C. 24–26.

5. Umarov S.Kh., Nuritdinov I., Ashurov J.Dzh., Khallokov F. Kh. Single Crystals of $TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe_2$ ($0 \leq x \leq 0.5$) Solid Solutions as Effective Materials for Semiconductor Tensometry // *Technical Physics Letters*. – Springer, 2017. – Vol.43, №8. –P. 730-732;

6. I. Nuritdinov, J. D. Ashurov, S. X. Umarov. Udelnoe soprotivlenie i tenzorezistivnie xarakteristiki kristallov tverdix rastvorov $TlIn_{1-x}Co_xSe_2$. //Materiali nauchno - prakticheskoy Respublikanskoy konferentsii s mejdunarodnim uchastiem «Aktualnie problemi prepodavaniya Fiziki». – Namangan, 2018. – C. 69 - 72.

7. Muller D., Eulenberger G., Hahn H. Uber ternare thallium-chalkogenidemit thalliumselenidestructures // *Zeitschrift für anorganische und allgemeine Chemie*. – Berlin, 1973. – No398. – P.207-220.

8. Lizarraga R., Ronneteg S., Berger R., Mohn P., Nordstrom L.,

Eriksson O. On the magnetic structure of TiCo_2Se_2 // Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials. – Elsevier, 2004. – P. 557–558.

9. Pikus G. E. Simmetriya i deformatsionnie effekti v poluprovodnikax. – Moskva: Nauka, 1973. – 548 c.